

ANALYSIS OF DULCIMER IN EASTERN EUROPE -- A CASE STUDY OF "CIMBALOM" IN HUNGARY**Xu Ke***Shandong University of Arts
master student, lecturer,
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Chimbaron, also known as "Hungarian Dulcimer". A string singing instrument. In 1874, it was reformed by the Hungarian instrument maker Schunda VencelJozsef (1845-1923) according to the Dussima, which was introduced into Europe in the Middle Ages and was popular in the 18th century, and was mostly used in small bands of gypsy in Eastern Europe. A wooden speaker with an irregular quadrilateral body, stretched with metal strings, which are struck by a hammer when played. It is large in size, supported by a detachable bracket and equipped with a sound pedal with a sound range of four octaves. This paper takes this instrument as an example to introduce the art of dulcimer in Eastern Europe.

Keywords: Eastern Europe, dulcimer art, Hungary, percussion style.

The Dulcimer originated in the Middle East, Asia, Persia and other ancient countries, and was later introduced into Spain, Turkey, Hungary and other countries, named Cimbalom. Now the dulcimer is a popular instrument in many countries around the world such as Romania, Britain, France, the United States, Iran, India, Iraq, Vietnam, North Korea, China, Japan and other countries, so the dulcimer is a universal and popular percussion string instrument with a wide range of world and distinct national character.

Mr. Xiang Zuhua, a famous contemporary dulcimer player and educator, divides the world dulcimer into three major systems according to the distribution and general situation of the dulcimer, which are: the Chinese dulcimer system, the West Asian and South Asian dulcimer system, and the European dulcimer system.

The European system includes all European countries and formerly European colonies in North America and Oceania, whose dulcimer names are mainly Desima, Lonteri, Simbaron, Hekburi and so on. In the 15th century, the dulcimer gradually spread in European countries, up to the court, down to the common people, and became a fashionable musical instrument in the Renaissance. The 15th century Dulicmer system of West Asia and South Asia in Europe, which is located in the Arab-Islamic culture and the cultural background of the Indian subcontinent, the dulcimer of this system is collectively called "Sengar". According to legend, it arrived in Iran in the 17th century and became a common instrument for court music, mainly used in Iranian muqam bands, playing Dastagh and accompanying art songs.

The Chinese dulcimer system includes the dulcimer of China and Korea, Japan, Mongolia, Thailand and Southeast Asia, whose dulcimer spread through China and was influenced by it. In China, the dulcimer is also known as the dulcimer, percussion qin, percussion qin, butterfly qin and so on. It is generally said that the dulcimer was introduced into China in the eighth year of Wanli in the Ming Dynasty (1580), which was initially popular in the coastal areas and gradually spread to the interior. In the late Qing Dynasty, the

court music was gradually declining, and folk instruments rose, and the dulcimer was absorbed into the various forms of local folk music. With the rise and increase of rap music and local opera, dulcimer is widely used as accompaniment for rap and opera. The earliest illustrated record of the dulcimer found so far is in the book *Okinawa and Chinese Art* written by the Ryukyu native Moriaki Kiina: In 1663, the Chinese envoys Zhang Xue-li went to Ryukyu and used the dulcimer (Yao Qin) in singing performances. In the appendix of the book, there are pictures of dulcimer playing. The player wears a Ming Dynasty costume and plays the instrument with a bamboo hand. The instrument has a trapezoid surface, and there are two instrument codes and carved patterns on the panel, indicating that the dulcimer was introduced into China in the 17th century and was relatively popular in the Ming Dynasty.

The European dulcimer system includes all European countries and former European colonies in North America and Oceania. The main names of Dulcimer are Desima Dulcimer, Cimbalom, Sateri Psaltery, Hackbrett and so on.

The name Desima is mainly used in English-speaking countries, from Greek and Latin. In 1139 AD, a book of ivory engravings in Byzantium, Turkey, contains a reference to Desima on the cover, which is the earliest picture of Desima ever found. The predecessor of the Desima was the Sateri, which was first used in Asia to sound by picking fingers or feathers. It was brought back to Europe by pilgrims and crusaders in the Middle Ages, all the way from Arabia to North Africa, and then to Spain and then to southern Europe; The other spread from Arabia to Turkey and northeastern Europe. Just in the Turkish Byzantine people changed the original plucked string to the pronunciation of the hand-held mallet striking the string, the harp body evolved into a trapezoidal box, and the Decima percussion string instrument began to be shaped into the dulcimer in the 12th and 13th centuries, and was spread to European countries.

Sarteri comes from the Greek word for "plucked", which refers to both the box-shaped instrument of plucked and the trapezoidal dulcimer, and the name has a complex polysemous phenomenon and is used in

Western European countries. Hekburi is the name of the dulcimer in German-speaking countries, in addition to Germany, it is also used in Swedish, Danzon, Swiss and so on. Shimbaro is mainly used in Eastern European countries, from the Greek word, specifically referring to percussion instruments. Hungary called Cimbalom, Romania called Tamba1, Poland called Cymbaly, Belarus called Tsimbali, Ukraine called Tsymbaly, Latvia called Cimbole, Lithuania called Cimboli, the Czech Republic called Cymboli. Similar names include Cemballo in Italy, ympanon in France, and Timpanon in Spain. All of the above names come from variations of the Greek Kymbalon.

What is the dulcimer system in Europe?

The European dulcimer system includes all European countries and formerly European colonies in North America and Oceania. The main names of dulcimer are Desima, Longteri, Himbaro, Hekburi and so on. In the 15th century, the dulcimer gradually spread in European countries, up to the court, down to the common people, and became a fashionable musical instrument in the Renaissance. In the period of classical music, the European dulcimer began to flourish, and professional composers created many dulcimer sonatas, concertos and quartets. Dulcimer has also become an important instrument in Eastern European folk bands and gypsy bands

What is the West Asia-South Asia dulcimer system?

The West Asia-South Asia dulcimer system is located in the context of Arab-Islamic culture and Indian subcontinent culture. This system of dulcines, commonly known as "Sengar", is said to have arrived in Iran in the 17th century and became a common instrument for court music, mainly used in Iranian muqam bands, playing Dastagh and accompanying art songs. Dulcimer is also very popular in Iraq, and television stations often broadcast dulcimer programs for the "Baghdad Band", which plays instrumental improvisations of Taksim and Iraqi muqam music. The dulcimer of the Turkish Caucasus also plays an important role in local folk music. The South Asian dulcimer has a short history, and after reform, the Indian dulcimer is also good at performing the glisson rhyme of "gra". This system of dulcimer body is small, narrow range, using a single mobile tone code for easy to move the tone change, left code on both sides of the octave, with a lighter mallet hit the string. Its rhythm mode is more complex, the Arab dulcimer has 24 equal rhythm, and the Indian Dulcimer has 22 notes in every octave, forming an exotic color and style completely different from the European and Chinese dulcimer.

What is the Chinese dulcimer system?

The Chinese dulcimer system, including the dulcimer of Korea, Japan, Mongolia, Thailand and Southeast Asia, is derived from the translated sound of the Chinese dulcimer. The names of the Chinese dulcimer are: Dulcimer, dulcimer, butterfly dulcimer, etc. The earliest illustrated record of the dulcimer found so far is in the book *Okinawa and Chinese Art*, written by the Ryukyu native Moriaki Kiina: In 1663, the Chinese envoys Zhang Xue-li went to Ryukyu and used the dulci-

mer (Yao Qin) in singing performances. In the appendix of the book is a picture of a dulcimer playing, dressed in Ming Dynasty costumes, with a trapezoidal surface and a bamboo instrument (Qin LAN). On the panel there are two piano codes and carved patterns. This shows that the dulcimer was already introduced to our country in the 17th century and was relatively popular in the Ming Dynasty.

The Hungarian dulcimer belongs to the European dulcimer system. After the War of Independence in 1848, it became one of the cultural symbols of the Hungarian nation. Dulcimer percussion tool we call "qin Zhu", it is named by the material (bamboo), but also has other different names, including "key" and "hammer" and so on. The hammer of the Simbaron is called "cimbalomverok", and the head of the hammer is relatively larger than that of the dulcimer, and the wrapping method and material of the hammer head are also different. Because of the wrapping, the hammer head of the simbaron is much larger and heavier than the bamboo head of the dulcimer. The percussion tool can not only be made of different materials, but also the hammer head can be wrapped in different materials to show a variety of timbre.

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